

A STUDY ON PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF RIVER UKE, KARU LOCAL GOVERNMENT, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study assessed the physico-chemical parameters of river Uke in Nasarawa state, Nigeria, with a view to evaluating water quality status. Water samples were collected from selected sampling stations along the river over a period of one year covering both dry and rainy seasons. Standard analytical procedures were employed for the determination of key physico-chemical parameters which include temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, total dissolved solid, turbidity, nitrate, and phosphate. Results revealed that the physico-chemical parameters of river Uke varies spatially and seasonally, reflecting the influence of environmental factors such as rain fall, runoff and anthropogenic activates. Water temperature ranges within 28.00-25.83 values of a typical tropical fresh water system while pH values (6.00-7.78) indicate slightly acidic to neutral condition suitable for aquatic life. Dissolved oxygen concentrations were generally within (4.6-6.13) which is acceptable limits for fish survival although occasionally changes were observed across station. Other parameters such as turbidity which ranges with in (58.55-47) and total dissolved oxygen which ranges within (2.28-00.46) showed higher values during the rainy season, likely due to increased surface runoff and sediment input into the river, nitrate and phosphate which values ranges from 2.28-0.46 and 27.07-0.58 respectively. From the one way ANOVA statistical analysis between parameters of different stations, the temperature, pH, total dissolved solid, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, nitrate and phosphate parameters showed no significant effects ($P \geq 0.05$) across three sampling stations with p-values of 0.640, 0.722, 0.924, 0.87, 0.818, 0.752, 0.922 and 0.976 respectively at 0.05 probability level. However, for the seasonal variations a T-test analysis was carried out which recorded that there were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) in temperature, pH, Turbidity, DO, BOD, nitrate and phosphate parameters between the two seasons while TDS showed no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) between the two seasons. This research contributes to the understanding of fresh water ecology in Nasarawa state and provides base line information essential for environmental monitoring, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable utilization of aquatic resources

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Fisheries play an important role in the agro-based economics by providing nutrition, increasing employment opportunities and earning foreign exchange (Mannan *et al.*, 2020). Fish is an important dietary animal protein source in human nutrition Abbas *et al.* (2019). In order to maintain sustainable fishery and improve the socio-economic conditions of fishing communities, it is essential to maintain the fish production at threshold through managing the water quality (Mannan *et al.*, 2020). Water quality is affected by anthropogenic waste discharge, which in turn affects pollutant concentrations and physicochemical variables and ultimately ecological processes such as the nutrient cycles, primary production, trophic relationships and consumer-species dynamics (Barlett *et al.*, 2019). In particular the effect of eutrophication of ecosystems caused by nutrients from rivers and discharge from human activities on fish assemblages result to species depletion. Eutrophication may positively affect fish assemblage by increasing secondary production through a bottom-up trophic cascade or may negatively affect fish assemblage by subjecting fish to physiological stress or hypoxia (Nelson *et al.*, 2019).

Temperature can exert great control over aquatic communities. If the overall water body temperature of a system is altered, an aquatic community shift can be expected. In water

above 30 degree Celsius, a suppression of all benthic organisms can be expected. Also different plankton groups will flourish under different temperatures (Arunkumar *et al.*, 2019). The pH is an indicator of the existence of biological life as most of them thrive in a quite narrow and critical pH range. The pH scale commonly ranges from 0 to 14. The scale is not linear but rather it is logarithmic (Purier *et al.*, 2021). A solution with a pH of 6 is ten times more acidic than a solution with a pH of 7. Pure water is said to be neutral, with a pH of 7. Water with a pH below 7.0 is considered acidic while water with pH greater than 7.0 is considered basic or alkaline (Guillermo *et al.*, 2022). Dissolved Oxygen is essential for aquatic life. A low Dissolved Oxygen (less than 2mg/l) would indicate poor water quality and thus would have difficulty in sustaining many sensitive aquatic lives.

The concentration of D.O. in epilimnetic waters continually equilibrates with the concentration of atmospheric oxygen to maintain 100% D.O. saturation (Islam *et al.*, 2022). Excessive algae growth can over-saturate (greater than 100% saturation) the water with D.O. when the rate of photosynthesis is greater than the rate of oxygen diffusion to the atmosphere. Excess turbidity leads to fewer photosynthetic organisms available to serve as food sources for many invertebrates. As a result, overall invertebrate numbers may also decline, which may then lead to a fish population decline. If

turbidity is largely due to organic particles, dissolved oxygen depletion may occur in the water body. The excess nutrients available will encourage microbial breakdown, a process that requires dissolved oxygen. In addition, excess nutrients may result in algal growth. Although photosynthetic by day, algae respire at night, using valuable dissolved oxygen. Fish kills often result from extensive oxygen depletion (Dandong *et al.*, 2019).

The total dissolved solids (TDS) in water consist of inorganic salts and dissolved materials. In natural waters, salts are chemical compounds comprised of anions such as carbonates, chlorides, sulphates, and nitrates (primarily in ground water), and cations such as potassium (K), magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), and sodium (Na). In ambient conditions, these compounds are present in proportions that create a balanced solution. If there are additional inputs of dissolved solids to the system, the balance is altered and detrimental effects may be seen. Inputs include both natural and anthropogenic source (Barlett *et al.*, 2019). Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) is a measure of organic pollution to both waste and surface water. High BOD is an indication of poor water quality. Biological Oxygen Demand represents the quantity of oxygen which is consumed in the course of aerobic processes of decomposition of organic materials, caused by microorganisms. The BOD therefore provides information on the biologically convertible Proportion of the organic content of a sample of

water. This leads to the consideration of the materials in terms of their susceptibility to oxidation by the use of oxygen.

The growth of macrophytes and phytoplankton is stimulated principally by nutrients such as nitrates. Many bodies of freshwater are currently experiencing influxes of nitrogen and phosphorus from outside sources. The increasing concentration of available phosphorus allows plants to assimilate more nitrogen before the phosphorus is depleted. Thus, if sufficient phosphorus is available, high concentrations of nitrates will lead to phytoplankton (algae) and macrophyte (aquatic plant) production. This is mostly due to the usage of fertilizers. Phosphate levels in excess of the recommended limits may harm aquatic life, although the ammonia molecule is a nutrient required for life, excess ammonia may accumulate in the organism and cause alteration of metabolism or increases in body pH. It is an indicator of pollution from the excessive usage of rich fertilizers. Gorde and Jadhav (2021) conducted a review on the assessment of Water Quality Parameters. Water is the most important in shaping the land and regulating the climate. It is one of the most important compounds that profoundly influence life. The quality of water usually described according to its physical, chemical and biological characteristics. Rapid industrialization and indiscriminate use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture are causing heavy and varied

pollution in aquatic environment leading to deterioration of water quality and depletion of aquatic biota. Due to use of contaminated water, human population suffers from water borne diseases. It is therefore necessary to check the water quality at regular interval of time. Parameters that may be tested include temperature, pH, turbidity, BOD, DO, nitrates and phosphates.

Uke River is Perennial River that flow through Uke town which is fast developing due to its proximity to Abuja, the Federal capital territory. This urbanization leads to increase in discharge of sewage, domestic and industrial wastes and effluent into the river. This will affect the physiochemical parameter of the water, thereby having negative effect on fisheries resources of the river. The need to conduct research on the status of physiochemical parameter on fish species diversity and their condition becomes inevitable. This study provide baseline information on the current state of physiochemical parameter which will further help to enact appropriate laws that will prevent discharge of municipal wastes into the water body by the appropriate authorities

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Uke is a town in Karu Local Government of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. It is located at 8.927.70(Lt/Long.). The river is located close to various fish farms where the source of water for the farm usage is gotten from the river. All the

effluents from the farm are also discharged directly into the river, containing great amount of nutrient which will definitely affect the physico-chemical parameters and biodiversity of the river.

2.2 Sampling Site

Three (3) sampling sites were selected from Uke River. Site one, site two and site three.

Study site 1

This site was approximately 100m from site 2.

Study site 2

The distance between site 1 and site 2 was approximately 100m.

Study site 3

The distance between site 2 and site 3 was about 100m.

2.3 Physico-chemical Parameter of Water

Physico-chemical characterization of river such us, Nitrate values, B.O.D, Temperature, pH, Dissolved oxygen (DO), total dissolved solid (T.D.S) was analyzed, all water samples were collected on same day and kept in rubber bottles washed with 10% HNO₃.The rubber bottles was labeled and immediately few drops of HNO₃ was added in order to prevent bacterial and fungal growth. Temperature and pH of water samples was measured at the time of collection.

2.4 Temperature

The temperatures were determined in the field using an analog clinical thermometer of the LaMotte aquaculture test kit. The water was taken by lowering the electrode of the thermo

meter into the water at immersion level for 3-5 minutes and removed, reading was taken immediately. The reading was recorded in degree Celsius (Colt and Tomasso, 2016).

2.5 Potential of Hydrogen (pH)

A test sample were filled with 5ml of sample, 10 drops of the range of pH indicator was added, then capped and mixed. Wide range pH octa-slide bar was inserted into the octa-slide viewer, then the test tube containing the solution was also inserted into the oct-slide viewer to match color of the sample with a standard color of the wide range pH octa-slide was recorded (Huent, 2019).

2.6 Nitrate

Test tube were filled to 2.5ml with sample, it was diluted with mixed acid reagent to 5ml, then 0.1g of colour developing reagent was added using 0.1g spoon, capped and allowed to mix for some minutes, nitrate nitrogen octa-slide bar was inserted into the octa-slide viewer, then the test tube containing the solution was inserted into the octa-slide viewer to match colour the samples with a standard colour of the nitrate nitrogen on the octa-slide bar, reading were taken from the octa-slide viewer and was recorded as NO₃N as ppm (Santhosh and Sigh, 2021)

2.7 Phosphate

Test tube were filled with 15ml of sample water then 1 drop of phenolphthalein indicator (1%) then 3 drops of chlorine reagent was added, capped and mixed until the solution turns yellow, then direct reading indicator was filled

with chlorine reagent and inserted into the center hold of the test tube, while gently swirling the test the plunger of the direct reading titrator was titrated into the test tube until the solution changes from yellow to orange red. Reading was taken directly from the direct titration scale and recorded as phosphate in mg/l (Mustapha, 2020)

2.8 Dissolved Oxygen

Water sample were collected in an aspirator bottle and free of bubbles and capped immediately, it was checked again to ensure no air bubble are trapped inside, then the cap was removed and 8 drops of Magnesium sulphate solution was added, 8 drops of alkaline potassium iodide oxide reagent was added, then capped and mixed inverting several times, a precipitate was formed and was allowed to settle below the bottle shoulder. Then 8 drops of sulphuric acid 1:1 was added, capped and shade gently for precipitate to dissolve and a clear yellow to brown-orange was developed and the sample was preserved. A test tube was filled to 20ml with the preserved water sample, then 8 drops of starch indicator solution was added and the solution turns blue and the cap was replaced, then direct reading titration was filled with sodium thiosulphate and be inserted into the center hold of the test tube, while gently swirling the tube, the plunger of the direct reading titration was titrated into the test tube until the solution changes from blue to faint yellow. Reading was taken from the direct

reading titration scale and Dissolved Oxygen recorded in ppm (Mustapha, 2021).

2.9 Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)

Water sample were collected from the study site using two bottles; the dissolve oxygen content of one bottle was examined and recorded as initial DO. The second sample bottle was kept in the incubator at 20 degree Celsius for 5 days after which the DO content of the water was determined using a simple formula

$$BOD = \text{Initial DO} - \text{Final DO}$$

2.10 Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)

3.0 RESULTS

Table 1: Physico-chemical parameter interactions of the sampling stations of river Uke

Physico-chemical parameters	Stations			P-value
	I	II	III	
Temperature(°c)	26.69±0.68	26.72±0.65	26.46±0.86	0.640
pH	6.46±0.68	6.39±0.69	6.5±0.56	0.722
TDS(mg/l)	30.18±2.31	30.53±4.22	31.36±4.14	0.924
Turbidity(mg/l)	52.25±3.33	51.38±4.13	51.57±5.03	0.870
Dissolved oxygen(mg/l)	5.69±0.61	5.52±0.79	5.51±0.89	0.818
BOD(mg/l)	2.10±0.74	2.25±0.38	2.10±0.42	0.752
Nitrate(mg/l)	1.19±0.71	1.24±0.58	1.30±0.68	0.922
Phosphate(mg/l)	1.16±0.68	1.15±0.65	1.20±0.59	0.976

3.1 Temperature (Degree Celcius) Parameter

The analysis of the temperature parameter on table 1, revealed that there were no significant

TDS was determined by using TDS meter by dipping the probes into the water until the screen shows a fix reading.

2.11 Data Analysis

One way analysis of variance (One-ANOVA) was used to analyze the monthly variations between the parameters studied at the three different sampled stations while T-test was used to analyze the data collected for seasonal variations (Dry and rainy Season) and Person’s correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine how the observed parameters were correlated to each other.

effects ($P \geq 0.05$) between the temperatures of station I, station II and station III ($P = 0.640$) across three sampling stations along river Uke. The monthly variations among temperatures

between months of March 2025 to February 2026 showed no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) statistically. Although, the means with the highest temperatures were recorded in the months of January, 2026 (27.46°C) and December, 2025 (27.43°C). The month of July, 2025 recorded the lowest temperature mean of 26.13°C as shown on table 2. The result of Pearson correlation analysis of physico-chemical parameters of river Uke during the period of study showed weak positive correlations between temperature with pH ($r=0.303$) and TDS ($r = 0.186$) and with negative correlations between turbidity ($r = -0.502$), DO ($r = -0.638$), BOD ($r = -0.328$), nitrate ($r = -0.281$), and Phosphorus ($r = -0.463$) at river Uke.

3.2 Potential of Hydrogen (pH)

The analysis of the potential of hydrogen parameter revealed that there were no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) between the pH of the three sampled stations because p-value (0.722) is greater than the P (0.05). Therefore it was concluded no significant effects in means of the pH among the three stations as recorded on table 1. The pH parameter between months on table 2 showed significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) with a p-value of 0.000. The month of February, 2026 and January, 2026 recorded the highest pH values with a pH of 7.78 and 7.31 respectively while the lowest pH values were observed in the month of May, 2025 (5.96) and July, 2025 (5.97). The correlation analysis for pH showed

there were weak positive correlations between pH and temperature ($r=0.303$) and TDS ($r=0.180$) with negative relationships with turbidity ($r=-0.536$), DO ($r=-0.551$), BOD ($r=-0.387$), nitrate ($r=-0.478$) and phosphate ($r=-0.361$) at river Uke.

3.3 Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)

The analysis of the TDS parameter revealed that there were no significant effects ($P \geq 0.05$) in means of TDS of the three sampled stations at river Uke. The p-value (0.924) recorded is greater than the P (0.05). Therefore it was concluded no significant differences in means of TDS of Station I, Station II, and Station III across the months sampled as recorded on table 1. The monthly variations of TDS as recorded on table 2 showed no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$). The TDS recorded a P-value of 0.175 which was greater than 0.05. However, the months with the highest TDS values during the period of the study were observed in the month of March, 2025 (33.96 mg/l) and October, 2025 (33.10 mg/l) and the month with the lowest value was recorded in the month of May, 2025 (26.13 mg/l) as documented on table 2. The result of Pearson correlation analysis of physico-chemical parameters of river Uke during the period of study showed. There were weak positive relationships between TDS with temperature ($r = 0.186$), pH ($r=0.180$) and phosphate ($r = 0.005$) while negative correlations were observed between TDS and turbidity ($r = -$

0.219), DO ($r=-0.348$), BOD ($r = -0.319$) and nitrate ($r = -0.25$) at river Uke.

3.4 Turbidity

The analysis of the turbidity parameter on table 1 revealed that there were no significant effects ($P \geq 0.05$) because p-value (0.87) is greater than the P (0.05). Therefore it was concluded no significant differences among the means of turbidity of the three stations; Station I, Station II, and Station III at river Uke. The monthly turbidity variations of river Uke during the period of the study showed significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) statistically. The month of August, 2025 recorded the highest mean value of 58.50 mg/l while the months of March, 2025 and January, 2026 recorded the lowest mean of 47.00 mg/l respectively as shown of table 2. The correlation analysis result of turbidity showed strong positive relationships between DO ($r = 0.757$) and phosphate ($r=0.747$) and weak positive relationships between nitrate ($r = 0.324$) and BOD ($r = 0.324$). Negative correlations were observed between turbidity with temperature ($r=-0.502$), pH ($r =-0.536$) and TDS ($r=-0.219$) at river Uke.

3.5 Dissolve Oxygen (DO)

The analysis of the DO parameter across the three stations at river Uke revealed that there were no significant effects ($P \geq 0.05$) as recorded on table 1 with a P value of 0.818. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05, therefore it was concluded there were no significant effects in means of DO among station I, station II, and station III. Table 2 recorded the

monthly variations among the DO of river Uke and the results revealed that there were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) among the DO observed during the study. Month of August 2025 recorded the highest mean value of DO (6.17 mg/l) and the month of January, 2026 recorded the lowest mean of 4.65 mg/l. The correlation analysis of DO parameter showed a strong positive correlation between turbidity ($r = 0.757$) and moderate positive correlations between nitrate ($r=0.601$), phosphate ($r = 0.671$) and a weak positive correlation with BOD ($r = 0.308$). Negative correlations were observed between DO and Temperature ($r = -0.638$), pH ($r= -0.551$) and TDS ($r = -0.348$) at river Uke.

3.6 Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)

The one-way ANOVA conducted to compare biological oxygen demand across three sampling stations along river Uke recorded that there were no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) among the means of the three sampled stations ($P=0.752$). Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 it was concluded there no significant effects in mean of BOD among the three stations; Station I, Station II, and Station III across the months sampled as recorded on table 1. The monthly variation of BOD as recorded on table 2 showed no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) with a p-value of 0.061. However, it was recorded that the month with the highest mean of BOD was that of April, 2025 (2.66 mg/l) while the lowest mean was recorded in the month of June and July, 2025

(0.30 mg/l). The BOD parameter showed weak positive correlations with nitrate ($r = 0.076$), turbidity ($r = 0.324$), DO ($r = 0.308$) and phosphate ($r = 0.237$). Negative correlations were observed between BOD with temperature ($r = -0.328$), pH ($r = -0.87$), and TDS ($r = -0.319$) at river Uke.

3.7 Nitrate

The result of the analysis of nitrate parameter on table 1 recorded that there were no significant effects ($P \geq 0.05$) among the means of the sampled stations (0.922). Since the p value 0.922 is greater than 0.05, therefore it was concluded no significant differences in means of nitrate among the three stations across the months sampled. Table 2 showed the monthly variations of phosphate parameter and the result recorded that there were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) among the phosphate parameters of the different months. The highest mean value was recorded in the month of October, 2025 (2.28 mg/l) while the month with the lowest mean were the month of March, 2025 (0.46 mg/l) and that of and January, 2026 (0.47 mg/l) respectively. The nitrate parameter showed a strong positive correlation with turbidity ($r = 0.711$), moderate positive relationships with DO ($r = 0.601$) and phosphate ($r = 0.673$) with a weak positive correlation with BOD ($r = 0.076$) while negative correlations were observed between nitrate and temperature ($r = -0.281$), pH ($r = -0.478$) and TDS ($r = -0.029$) at river Uke.

3.8 Phosphate

The result of the analysis of the phosphate parameter revealed that there were no significant effects ($P \geq 0.05$) among the phosphate parameter of the three sampled stations with a P- value of 0.976 which is greater than 0.05. It was concluded that no significant differences in the means as recorded on table 1. As documented on table 2 there were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) in the phosphate parameters observed on monthly basis with a P-value of 0.000. The highest mean values where recorded in the month of October,

2025 (3.30 mg/l) and July, 2025 (2.08 mg/l) while the months with the lowest means were the months of March, 2025 (0.58 mg/l) and that of April, 2025 (0.68 mg/l). There was also a strong positive correlation between phosphate with turbidity ($r = 0.747$), moderate positive correlations with DO ($r = 0.671$) and nitrate ($r = 0.673$). A weak positive correlation with BOD ($r = 0.005$) and negative correlations with temperature ($r = -0.463$) and pH ($r = 0.361$) at river Uke.

Figure 1: Physico-chemical parameters interactions of the sampling stations of river Uke for March 2025 to February 2026.

Table 2: Monthly Physico-chemical Parameter interactions at River Uke during the Period of the Study (March 2025 to February, 2026)

Physico-chemical parameters	Months												P-value
	March	April	May	June	July	August	Sept.	October	Nov.	Dec.	Jan	Feb	
Temperature	27.03 ^a	26.17 ^a	26.2 ^{7^a}	26.2 ^{7^a}	26.1 ^{3^a}	26.40 ^a	26.4 ^{7^a}	26.23 ^a	27.2 ^{7^a}	27.4 ^{3^a}	27. ^{46^a}	26. ^{33^a}	0.067
pH	6.07 ^a	6.10 ^a	5.96 ^a	6.40 ^{ab}	5.97 ^a	6.20 ^a	6.03 ^a	6.06 ^a	6.45 ^a	7.07 ^b	7.3 ^{1^c}	7.7 ^{8^c}	0.000
TDS	33.10 ^a	29.13 ^a	26.1 ^{3^a}	27.7 ^{0^a}	29.5 ^{6^a}	31.00 ^a	30.4 ^{3^a}	33.96 ^a	30.1 ^{3^a}	33.4 ^{0^a}	30. ^{76^a}	32. ^{93^a}	0.175
Turbidity	47.00 ^a	51.83 ^{cde}	51.16 ^{bcd}	55.3 ^{3^{ef}}	55.4 ^{6^{ef}}	58.50 ^f	55.16 ^{def}	55.03 ^{def}	49.5 ^{0^{abc}}	47.3 ^{3^{ab}}	47. ^{00^a}	47. ^{50^a}	0.000

DO	4.90 ^a	5.47 ^{ab}	6.00 ab	6.03 ab	6.13 ab	6.17 ^{ab}	6.01 ^a b	6.43 ^b	5.30 ^a b	4.83 ^a	4.6 5 ^a	4.9 0 ^a	0.00 1
BOD	2.10 ^{ab}	2.66 ^d	2.6 ^b	0.30 ab	0.3 0 ^{ab}	2.26 ^{ab}	2.43 ^a b	2.17 ^{ab}	1.80 ^a b	1.27 ^a	2.0 5 ^{ab}	1.9 0 ^{ab}	0.06 1
Nitrate	0.46 ^a	0.93 ^a b	1.02 ^a bc	1.63 ^c de	1.45 bcd	1.80 ^{de}	1.76 ^d e	2.28 ^e	1.88 ^e	0.69 a	0.4 7 ^a	0.5 5 ^a	0.00 0
Phosphate	0.58 ^a	0.68 ^a	1.01 ^a	1.1 ^a	2.08 c	1.91 ^c	1.30 ^a b	3.30 ^c	0.78 ^a	0.73 ^a	0.7 2 ^a	0.7 5 ^a	0.00 0

Note: Values with different superscripts along the rows were significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Table 3: Table Seasonal Variation of Physico-Chemical Parameters of River Uke

Physico-chemical parameters	Seasons		P-value
	Dry	Rainy	
Temperature(°C)	26.95±0.78	26.29±0.48	0.005
pH	6.79±0.71	6.11±0.23	0.000
TDS(mg/l)	31.58±3.71	29.80±3.34	0.140
Turbidity(mg/l)	48.36±2.19	55.11±2.45	0.000
Dissolved Oxygen(mg/l)	5.01±0.63	6.14±0.29	0.000
BOD(mg/l)	1.96±0.56	2.34±0.41	0.028
Nitrate(mg/l)	0.83±0.53	1.66±0.45	0.000
Phosphate(mg/l)	0.71±0.20	1.62±0.56	0.000

Table 3 above shows the seasonal variation of physico-chemical parameters of river Uke. T-test analysis was carried out to determine the seasonal variations of physico-chemical parameters at river Uke for dry and rainy seasons. The results as represented on the table revealed that there were significant differences in most of the observed parameters across the seasons. The highest pH mean value (6.79) was observed in dry season while the lowest pH mean value (6.11) was recorded in rainy season. For the Total dissolved solid (TDS) there were no

significant differences between the two seasons. The temperature parameter recorded a significant effect ($P \leq 0.05$) between the two seasons with a P-value of 0.005. The highest mean value was recorded in dry season (26.95°C) while the lowest mean was observed in the rainy season (26.29°C). There were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) among the pH parameters for the two seasons observed. There were no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) between the two seasons ($P = 0.140$). However, the highest mean value of TDS was recorded in the dry season (31.58 mg/l) while the lowest mean

value of TDS was recorded in the rainy season (29.80 mg/l). The result of the T-test analysis of turbidity between the two seasons revealed there were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) with a P-value of 0.000. The rainy season recorded the highest mean value of 55.11 mg/l as against that of the dry season which recorded the mean value of 48.36 mg/l. The DO parameter between the two seasons also recorded significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) with a P-value of 0.000. The highest mean value of DO was recorded in the rainy season (6.14 mg/l) while the lowest was recorded in dry season with a mean of 5.01 mg/l. Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) among the two season also showed lowest mean value in the dry season (0.71 mg/l).

significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) with a P-value of 0.028. The highest mean value of the two seasons was recorded in rainy season (2.34 mg/l) while the dry season recorded the lowest mean value (1.96mg/l). The nitrate and phosphorus parameters also recorded significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) between the two seasons with a P-value of 0.000 respectively. The highest mean value for nitrate parameter was observed in rainy season (1.66 mg/l) and the lowest mean was recorded in dry season (0.83mg/l). The phosphorus parameter on the other hand also recorded its highest mean in rainy season (1.62 mg/l) and the

Figure 2: Means of Seasonal Variations of Physico-Chemical Parameters of River Uke for March 2025 to February 2026

4.0 DISCUSSION

The findings of the water quality parameter collected from the research stations showed temperature has a significant impact on the chemical and physical properties of water. The results were somehow consistent with earlier data stating that tropical temperatures range from 28 to 25°C (Atobatele and Ugwumba, 2022). The difference in temperature might be due to early wet season weather condition in April to June when atmospheric temperature was a little high during raining season. Water's hydrogen ion concentration (pH) is significant because many biological processes can only take place within a limited pH range (Ahmed, 2023). Thus, aquatic species may die if a variation exceeds the allowed range. Thus, the pH found in this study is within the permissible range of 6.0-7.78 for cultivating tropical fish species and the values advised for drinking water (WHO, 2012). In march, April may June July august September October November, December, January, February respectively, the values of dissolved oxygen in the three station A, B, C had the mean of 5.78, 5.42, 5.51 respectively. Because most species, save from anaerobic microorganisms, rapidly decline when oxygen levels in waterfalls, dissolved oxygen (DO) has main importance as a limiting element in natural water. Oxygen plays the most important role in determining the potential biological quality of water. The quantity of oxygen needed for a contaminant's biological degradation is known as the

biological oxygen demand (BOD). It is frequently used to gauge the concentration of contaminants in natural and waste waters and to determine how strong different types of waste, including sewage and industrial effluent, are Zeb *et al.*, (2021). Based on the principles that readings of less than 2 mg L are clean, 3 - 5 mg/L are moderately clean, and 10 mg/L are unquestionably awful and contaminated, BOD is a good assessment of the quality of any water (Idowu and Gadzama, 2023). This research found that the average BOD levels were less than 5 mg/l, which is a sign of reasonably clean water in the current investigation.

The study shows that greater amount of phosphate and nitrate concentrations may be due to both surface runoffs and the breakdown of organic materials with the values of 2.28-00.46 and 27.07-0.58 respectively. This was in line with the findings of Osimen *et al.* (2015), who reported higher value during the rainy season in Ojirami reservoir, but it was at odds with observations made by Usman *et al.* (2018) and Ibrahim *et al.* (2018), who reported higher value during the dry season in Lake Alau and Kontagora reservoir. High levels of phosphate and nitrate can cause excessive algae development, endangering other aquatic life. The study shows during the period of the rainy season (April-October) due to increase in rainfall and surface I noticed lower temperature, higher turbidity, lower total dissolved solids, higher phosphate, and higher nitrate level, higher biological oxygen demand

and also higher dissolved oxygen lastly a lower PH level concentration. And also during the period of the study in the dry season (NOV – MAR), a higher temperature, lower turbidity, higher total dissolved solid, lower phosphate, lower nitrate level, lower biological oxygen demand, lower dissolved oxygen and higher PH was noticed during the period of time.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study investigated the physico-chemical parameters of water in River Uke, Nasarawa State, with the aim of understanding aquatic ecosystem health and biodiversity patterns in the river. The result indicated that key physico-chemical parameters such as temperature, pH, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, nitrate, phosphate, biological oxygen demand, varied seasonally. However most parameters remained within acceptable range for supporting healthy aquatic

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life suggesting the river Uke sustains generally favorable environments for fish survival and growth. Overall, the integration of physico-chemical data with biological indicators in this study underscores the importance of multidisciplinary approaches for assessing riverine health. River Uke supports a valuable fish community but variation in water quality parameters highlights the need for ongoing monitoring and management to safeguard ecological integrity. Awareness programs should be organized for local communities to educate them on the impact of these activities on water quality. Conservation and restoration of vegetation along river Uke should be encouraged. Vegetation buffers help reduce erosion control, nutrient inflow, improve water quality, and provide essential habitats for fish and other aquatic organisms.

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